

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIGITAL TRAVELERS AND TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The paper is an integral part of the project "Research on the use of digital products in the Georgian tourism sector" which won the internal grant projects competition of Grigol Robakidze University.

The aim of the article is to study the role of digital technologies among the digital travelers. The article demonstrates the current digital market and digital applications in tourism, which travelers are using while planning traveling and during the traveling itself. In the article are demonstrated the results of quantitative research, based on it, it can be said that digital technologies have completely changed the lifestyle of travelers, it has made traveling more flexible and affordable. The future is promisable, as applications are being developed and gaps which are identified while using digital technologies are eliminated, at the same time new functionalities are being implemented and their coming closer to answer the

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Introduction

Digital technologies are the trend nowadays and it is almost impossible to be competitive on the market if companies are not using digital technologies. Thus, nowadays a lot of applications and software are created that help business owners control their businesses and satisfy their customers. With the help of Artificial Intelligence software and applications, the business managing process is more complex, flexible and allows making hotels more customer orientated. The digital travelers themselves are actively using digital applications while traveling.

Computer-mediated technologies allow individuals, companies, NGOs, governments, and other organizations to view, create, and share information, ideas, career interests in virtual communities and networks. The use of the Internet and other information and communication technologies is ushering in a new era of global economy. The advent of digital tools has had a noticeable impact on tourism. A growing number of travelers plan their trips relying on online travel agencies (OTAs), digitally user-generated content (UGC) and other digital tools. Digitalization has also transformed the traditional roles of tourism producers and consumers, with new roles, relationships, business models, and competencies emerging. The rise of digital platforms has increased the variety and volume of tourism products, services and experiences, with on-demand functionality accelerating the speed of economic transactions, market awareness and feedback. These shifts have created new opportunities, as well as challenges, for tourism industry.

There are a lot of essential modern digital trends that those in the tourism industry need to be aware of, and adapt to, if they are going to successfully optimize business performance. Tourism business has to keep up with the latest digital trends, if they want to successfully operate on the market. In line with the new trends of traveling, there is a dynamically growing demand for

special tailor-made offers beyond mass tourism, as conscious consumers expect personalized solutions that answer their individual needs.

Literature Review

The industrial revolution, which began in the 1800s, was one of the most massive and global changes the world has seen, and it continues to shape in the present times. Revolution of the technologies is part of these changes. Advances in digitalization and Internet technologies are creating the new paradigm of industry, which is distinguished for rapid changes such as individualization on demand, increased ability of buyers to decide about the conditions of the exchange, more flexibility in the creation of products and services, decentralization with fast decision-making processes, efficient management of resources and sustainable approaches. It basically allows a strong technology-push in various industries and practices as well. These new processes bring a wide range of new trends related to short developing periods of products and services, and high innovation strategies that help many enterprises become successful [Gvaramadze 2022].

Technological advancements have brought great opportunities to the tourism industry as well. Easier access to the information through new technological advances has the potential to radically change the tourism industry. Tourist applications are in the seventh place in terms of downloads. 30% of consumers use a mobile app to book/buy a hotel, and 40% use a mobile app to book/buy airline tickets. These numbers grow every year. Internet advertising has had a significant impact on the management, promotion and sales processes of tourism companies. Therefore, on the perception of visitors who are planning trips using digital technologies [Gvaramadze 2022]. Virtual reality (VR) can be a powerful tool for destination marketing in the tourism industry. VR technology allows potential tourists to experience a destination before they book a trip, which can help them make more informed decisions about

where to travel. During the COVID pandemic, virtual tourism has become more popular around the world. For instance, to commemorate the 500th anniversary of Leonardo da Vinci's death in 2019, the Louvre Museum used virtual reality tours [Archi and Brahim Benbba 2023]. Moreover, apps like WalkinVR and Rendever provide accessible travel experiences for people with disabilities or mobility limitations, enabling them to explore the world without barriers. It is noteworthy that Cruise lines like Royal Caribbean and Carnival have started incorporating VR to enhance onboard experiences for their guests. Virtual reality (VR) is a powerful tool for destination marketing in the tourism industry. VR technology allows potential tourists to experience a destination before they book a trip, which can help them make more informed decisions about where to travel. Additionally, VR can allow visitors to improve their perceptions by considering hedonistic and emotional experiences [Archi and Brahim Benbba 2023]. However, the COVID 19 pandemic has clearly challenged the industry and its operations. Many companies have been negatively affected by important economic losses in millions of dollars and have had to deal also with losses of their workforce, who have chosen other, safer industries. The current situation is also affecting different communities and their destinations, which makes the entire industry re-think about problems and solutions, come up with changes and new innovations to recover, and be able to keep travelers safe and motivate them to travel to the touristic destinations [Muñoz 2023]. All things considered, digital innovation has become an essential element for tourism.

In addition, it is important to emphasize the process of sustainable tourism development. VR protects the environment from damage and pollution. On the other hand, it protects destinations from damage that can be caused by tourists, whether at the site's heritage, environmental or social level [Schmidt 2023]. For instance, National Geographic's VR app offers virtual safaris, allowing users to observe wildlife in their natural habitats. These experiences foster a greater appreciation for the natural world without disturbing ecosystems. Tourism industry is becoming more and more competitive day by day, that is the reason why tourism companies are trying to create and develop their own "Digital Ecosystem".

Besides, border control is a very important part of the tourism sector. The development of digital technologies facilitates these processes. For example, nowadays many airports use iris-scan, 3D facial recognition and touchless fingerprint scanners. This is the proof that in a few years, digital technologies will fundamentally change border management and create a huge opportunity for industry transformation [Kaspar al 2023].

The growth of role of digital technologies has become clearly in the Georgian market as well. In 2019,

22.6% of international visitors received information about Georgia from the internet, and in 2022 this figure increased by 25.5% [gnta.ge]. It is obvious that the Internet is one of the main ways of obtaining information. Representatives of the tourism sector actively use modern booking applications. Such mobile applications as Audio Guide Georgia, TravelGis, Expago, Biliki make the trip to Georgia even more interesting, comfortable and unforgettable for tourists. For example, the Audio Guide Georgia application performs the function of an audio guide and provides the services of a physical guide to tourists during excursion. It not only informs tourists about various history and places in detail, but also helps them to discover sightseeing from a completely different angle [Entrepreneur Georgia, 2023]. Very popular applications among Georgian travelers are TripAdvisor, Airbnb, Google Maps, HostelWorld, Uber, etc.

Overall, the decisive role of digital technologies in the modern tourism industry, including in the Georgian market, is obvious. Along with the increase in free time, expended energy and incomes, the desire for tourism products get higher. A good example of a solution to this, are electronic applications and digital devices, that save time and make travel much easier. At the same time as the development of technologies, the frequency and scale of their use increases.

Materials and methods

The research was conducted using materials provided by articles, research papers and literature reviews as well as books of Georgian and foreign scientists. Furthermore, a quantitative (structured questionnaire was developed) method was used to obtain information about consumer attitudes towards digital technologies. The target segment of travelers was selected for data collection. The sample was selected by random sampling. The sample represents a diverse range of demographic characteristics, including age, gender and education. 303 people took part in the survey (period – from 15th of July to 15th of August), from which 300 answers were valid. They were randomly selected respondents, who had a desire to take part in the research.

Data was collected by using online surveys that were distributed through various platforms such as social media, online forums and email invitations. Quantitative research participants were given clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaire. The confidentiality of the respondents is ensured.

The quantitative was analyzed, with SPSS, using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, cross tabulation and means.

Results and discussion

To summarize the results of the research, 300 people took part in the research, from which 54. 3% were women and 45.7% were men (see, Table1/ Gender).

Table 1.

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	163	54.3	54.3	54.3
	Male	137	45.7	45.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

According to the age statistics most of the travelers were from 35-44 age group - 47.0%; 45-54 - 23.7% ; 25-34 – 23.30% ; 18-24 – 4%. (see, Table 9. Age and Frequency of Traveling Cross tabulation).

Table 2.

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	12	4.0	4.0	4.0
	25-34	70	23.3	23.3	27.3
	35-44	141	47.0	47.0	74.3
	45-54	71	23.7	23.7	98.0
	55+	6	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

According to the collected data 34% of respondents were having bachelor's degree, 54% master degree, 11.7% PhD and 0.3% secondary education (see, Table 3. Education).

Table 3.

Education					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	102	34.0	34.0	34.0
	Master	162	54.0	54.0	88.0
	PhD	35	11.7	11.7	99.7
	Secondary education	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The statistics show that most of the interviewers 82% were working full time, 11.7% part time, 5% were self-employed and 1.30% unemployed (see, Table 4. Occupation).

Table 4.

Occupation					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Full time	246	82.0	82.0	82.0
	Part time	35	11.7	11.7	93.7
	Self employed	15	5.0	5.0	98.7
	Unemployed	4	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

What about income, 1% had income from 0-500 GEL, 0.70% - 501-1000 GEL, 11.30% 1001-1500; 34% - 1501-2000 GEL and 53% more than 2000+ (see, Table 5. Monthly Income)

Table 5.

Monthly Income					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0 – 500	3	1.0	1.0	1.0
	1001 – 1500	34	11.3	11.3	12.3
	1501 – 2000	102	34.0	34.0	46.3
	2000 +	159	53.0	53.0	99.3
	501 – 1000	2	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

According to the statistics of the frequency of traveling: 0.30% chose once in a month, seldom - 8.3%, once in quarter - 16.7, once in a year 35.7%, and twice in a year 39.0% and this was the highest percentage (see, Table 6. Frequency of Travelling).

Table 6.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once in a month	1	.3	.3	.3
	Once in a year	107	35.7	35.7	36.0
	Once in quarter	50	16.7	16.7	52.7
	Seldom	25	8.3	8.3	61.0
	Twice in a year	117	39.0	39.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The cross tabulation was done in order to see the relationship between monthly income and the frequency of traveling. And it has been shown that, twice in a year (70 individuals) and once in a year (50 individuals) travel the group of individuals who have income more than 2000+ GEL (see, Table 7. Monthly Income and Frequency of Travelling).

Table 7.

Monthly Income and Frequency of Traveling Cross tabulation							
Count							
		Frequency of Traveling					Total
		Once in a month	Once in a year	Once in quarter	Seldom	Twice in a year	
Monthly Income	0 – 500	0	0	1	2	0	3
	1001 – 1500	0	14	4	4	12	34
	1501 – 2000	0	42	16	10	34	102
	2000 +	1	50	29	9	70	159
	501 – 1000	0	1	0	0	1	2
Total		1	107	50	25	117	300

Note. Authors' according to the research

At the same time cross tabulation was done to see the gender and frequency of traveling. The results showed, that the most of the females (68) travel twice in a year and on the second place is once in a year (52 female). What about males, 49 of them, which is the highest number, travel also twice in a year. The results demonstrate, that people are planning traveling on vacation time, which mostly is twice in a year (see, Table 8).

Gender and Frequency of Traveling Cross tabulation). The cross tabulation was also done to see the age and frequency of traveling, the data showed, that mostly active were people from 35-44- 58 people who travel twice in a year and once in a year (49 people) (see, Table 9. Age and Frequency of Traveling Cross tabulation).

Table 9. Age and Frequency of Traveling Cross tabulation

Table 8.

Count							
		Frequency of Traveling					Total
		Once in a month	Once in a year	Once in quarter	Seldom	Twice in a year	
Gender	Female	1	52	21	21	68	163
	Male	0	55	29	4	49	137
Total		1	107	50	25	117	300

Note. Authors' according to the research

Table 9.

		Count					Total
		Frequency of Traveling					
		Once in a month	Once in a year	Once in quarter	Seldom	Twice in a year	
Age	18-24	0	4	4	4	0	12
	25-34	1	21	10	10	28	70
	35-44	0	49	28	6	58	141
	45-54	0	31	8	3	29	71
	55+	0	2	0	2	2	6
Total		1	107	50	25	117	300

Note. Authors' according to the research

The results of the research showed, that sources of getting information for 58% were friends and for 35% was social media (see, Table 10. Sources of getting information).

Table 10.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Friends	174	58.0	58.0	58.0
	Other	5	1.7	1.7	59.7
	Social Media	105	35.0	35.0	94.7
	Web-sites	16	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The question about priority while traveling demonstrated that 43.3% prefer traveling abroad and 44.7% both, abroad and in Georgia as well, only in Georgia preferred just 12% (see, Table 11. Priority while traveling).

Table 11.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Abroad	130	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Both	134	44.7	44.7	88.0
	Georgia	36	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The respondents were asked question about using travel agencies, the results demonstrated, that 2% were using tourism agencies, 30.3% were not and 67.7% are using it seldom (see, Table 12. Collaboration with tourism agencies).

Table 12.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	91	30.3	30.3	30.3
	Seldom	203	67.7	67.7	98.0
	Yes	6	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The frequency of using mobile apps statistics showed, that 86.3% were using them, 10% used them seldom and 0.7% did not use (see, Table 13. Using mobile applications while traveling).

Table 13.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	2	.7	.7	.7
	Seldom	39	13.0	13.0	13.7
	Yes	259	86.3	86.3	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The most popular web-site app appeared air bnb, which gives possibility to book the flat almost all over the world, at affordable price, then comes booking.com 27.7%; 2% of respondents book it directly from the hotel's web-site, which sometimes is cheaper (see, Table 14. Popular applications/ web-sites while traveling).

Table 14.

Popular applications/ web-sites while traveling					
Which application/website do you use to book the hotel?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Airbnb	209	69.7	69.7	69.7
	Booking.com	83	27.7	27.7	97.3
	Directly from Hotel's web-site	6	2.0	2.0	99.3
	Other	2	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

According to the research, the most popular web-sites / applications are directly airline companies' web-sites (73.3%), which mostly offer tickets with cheaper price, the second popular app (22.0%) is skyscanner, which gives us ability to search for the cheapest tickets all over the world (Table 15. Web-sites / Applications for buying tickets).

Table 15.

Web-sites / Applications for buying tickets					
Which application/website do you use to buy the ticket?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Directly from airlines web-site	220	73.3	73.3	73.3
	fly.ge	8	2.7	2.7	76.0
	Kiwi	1	.3	.3	76.3
	skyscanner	66	22.0	22.0	98.3
	other	5	1.7	1.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The apps which are mostly used by digital travelers are google travel (79%) and 18% answered that, they are downloading apps by country (see, the Table 16. Applications which are used while traveling).

Table 16.

Applications which are used while traveling					
Which application do you use mostly while traveling?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Google Travel	237	79.0	79.0	79.0
	It depends on the country	54	18.0	18.0	97.0
	Other	2	.7	.7	97.7
	Tripadvisor	7	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The research showed, that 83% had information about Georgian application and 17 did not (see, Table 17. Information about Georgian applications)

Table 17.

Information about Georgian applications					
Do you have information about Georgian applications?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	51	17.0	17.0	17.0
	Yes	249	83.0	83.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

Name the web-site, application, platform and etc. what you use firstly while planning to travel: Booking.com, cheap travel, wizzair.com, Maps.me, Tripadvisor, social media, trvelify, youtube. The research also showed that 152 female are using mobile apps and 107 men, in case of seldom frequency 9 female and 30 male and answer „no“ was marked by 2 respondents (see, Table 18. Gender and using mobile applications)

Table 18.

Gender and using mobile applications					
Gender and using mobile applications while traveling? Crosstabulation					
Count					
		Do you use mobile applications while traveling?			Total
		No	Seldom	Yes	
1.Gender	Female	2	9	152	163
	Male	0	30	107	137
Total		2	39	259	300

Note. Authors' according to the research

After all discussed data, the profile of Georgian Digital traveller was created (see, the Table 19. The Profile of Georgian Digital Traveler)

Table 19.

The Profile of Georgian Digital Traveler

Gender	Female
Age	35-44
Education	Master
Occupation	Full time
Monthly Income	2000+
Frequency of Traveling	Twice in a year / Once in a year
Sources of getting information	Friends / Social Media
Priority while traveling	Both: In Georgia and Abroad
Using mobile apps	Yes
Buying airline's tickets	Directly from the app/web-site
Apps while traveling	Google Travell

The Georgian Agency for Innovation and Technology's is funding various apps and innovations from various field. Since 2019 there were funded projects from hospitality too (see Table 20. Granted Projects from travel/tourism industry).

Table 20.

Granted Projects from travel/tourism industry

The type of Grant	Year	Beneficiary	The name of the project	Description of the project	Industry
Co-financing grants (100,000 GEL)	2019	Ltd. Travel Guide	Travel Guide	Tourism startup - "Travel Guide" represents an innovative tourism platform, the main goal of it is to develop the tourism sector by introducing innovative technologies.	travel/tourism
Co-financing grants (100,000 GEL)	2020	Ltd. Ofoodo	OFOODO	The goal of the project is to create a platform - OFOODO.com, which will provide access to both local and international visitors to food establishments throughout Georgia.	travel/tourism
Co-financing grants (100,000 GEL)	2020	Ltd. Revi Boxes	REVI BOXES	REVI BOXES will be developed in collaboration with both hotel management and F&B management experts, who will ensure efficiency in operations and technical work.	travel/tourism
Co-financing grants (100,000 GEL)	2021	Ltd. Brothers Trail	Mobile travel guide Biliki	The goal of the project is to create a global marketplace for travel itineraries that will help travelers plan their tours and enable them to share and sell the tours they have created.	travel/tourism
Co-financing grants (100,000 GEL)	2021	Ltd. Areal Guide	AReal Guide	Creating a digital guide software platform for museums.	travel/tourism
Co-financing grants (150,000 GEL)	2022	Ltd. eConsul	eConsul	The goal of the project is to create a space that will help the traveler to fill in, store and manage his personal information	travel/tourism

Innovative entrepreneurship grant program in pilot regions (up to 100,000 GEL)	2022	Ltd. Samkhari	Art Winery	The main purpose and essence of Art Winery is to give new life to the field of winemaking, using modern technology, specifically holograms.	travel/tourism
Small grants for pilot regions (up to 30 00 GEL)	2022	Ltd. With Love	Racha with Love	The purpose of the web platform "Racha With Love" is to improve service delivery in the tourism industry and create a technological solution that is tailored to the structure of the Georgian tourism industry.	travel/tourism
Small grants for pilot regions (up to 30 00 GEL)	2022	Ltd. horsetour	Platform horsetours.ge	The goal of the project is the development of equestrian tourism, which means the digitization of the sector and increasing its accessibility, both for the user and for the service provider.	travel/tourism

Note. Authors, according to the research, data received from Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency

Conclusions

In conclusion it can be said, that digital technologies, was completely changed the lifestyle of travelers. Travelers nowadays are not booking tickets or hotels at travel agencies as they were doing it before. They prefer to plan everything on their own, as in some cases it is cheaper and also it makes traveling more flexible, customer orientated. The discussed data, also showed that in Georgia, there are Georgian digital apps and GITA has also funded 9 of them, but Georgian travelers are getting used to use it while traveling in Georgia. The research also showed, that in case on Georgian digital apps market will offer web-site or mobile application, which will give possibility to book all hotels in Georgia, as it is booking.com or Airbnb, it can have a positive future. The research also showed, that wide range of applications are on international digital market and they are being developed, with the help of feedbacks.

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